

MADANIYATDAN HAYRATDA QOLISH

Ergasheva Saida Umidjon qizi

Andijon chet tillar instituti o`qituvchi

Atabayeva Mufazzalxon Roziqjon qizi

Andijon davlat chet tillar instituti

Ingliz tili va adabiyoti yo`nalishi 339-guruh talabasi

Annotatsiya: Madaniyatni hayratda qoldirish atamasi muammo va bezovtalik hissiyotlarini anglatadi. Tashqi madaniyat uchun ochilgan. Haqiqiy hayratlanarlilikning bu chegaraviy ta'rifidan tashqari, ibora qoshimcha ravishda muhojiming universal tajriba davomida boshdan kechiradigan jami tayyorgarligini tasvirlash uchun ishlatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatni hayratda qoldirish, madaniyatlararo muloqot, integratsiya, ko'p qirralilik, hayrat Taqdimot

CULTURE SHOCK

Ergasheva Saida Umidjon daughter

Teacher of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Atabayeva is the daughter of Mufazzalxon Roziqjon

Student of English language and literature group 339

Abstract: The term Culture Stun alludes to the emotions of trouble and unease when being uncovered to a outside culture. Other than this limit definition of the actual stun the expression is additionally utilized in arrange to depict the

total prepare a sojourner goes through amid an universal experience.

Key words: Culture stun, intercultural communication, integration, versatility, marvel.

КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ ШОК

Эргашева Саида Умиджон дочь

Преподаватель Андижанского государственного
института иностранных языков

Атабаева –дочь муфаззалхон Розикжон

Теоретическая: Термин «Культурное оглушение» указывает на эмоции беспокойства и беспокойства, когда раскрыты для внешней культуры. Помимо этого предельного определения фактического оглушения, это выражение также используется для описания полной подготовки, через которую проходит путешественников условияхуниверсального опыта.

Ключевые слова: культурный шок межкультурная коммуникация, интеграция, многогранность, чудо.

The term "culture stun" refers to the effect of transitioning from one familiar culture to another. This effect includes the unease and feelings (such as surprise, perplexity, vulnerability, and perplexity) experienced. when a person has to adapt to a complex and varied social or interpersonal context. Culture shock is a change you could experience after being exposed to a new environment and a better way of living. Culture shock is the experience of feeling uncomfortable or, in some situations, truly abandoned while abroad, for instance, during family gatherings like Christmas. Culture shock may be a marvel with broad implications. The social

decay it implies can lead to alcoholism, drug addiction, suicide, wantonness, misbehavior, and viciousness.

The Presentation Organize The Presentation Organize is the essential organize in affirmation. In the midst of this organize, you begin to get it why things are depleted a certain way. You start to respect the culture and traditions, whether you consider them to be incredible or horrendous. You begin to feel more comfortable in your present day environment, and you start to have a more positive viewpoint. You're feeling more certain and superior orchestrated to oversee with any issues that might rise. Be beyond any doubt that culture shock isnt a wonderfully coordinate experience; you'll return to the Trouble Orchestrate distinctive times until you hit...

The Alteration Orchestrate In the midst of this organize, your state of intellect changes and you're able to function in both social orders, You've got got gotten a handle on the unused culture and are able to see it in a advanced, in any case sensible, light. In this organize you're routinely well-oriented to your unused life, and have made your have affinities and plans. You are feeling comfortable, beyond any doubt, and competent of making choices. You not feel alone and disengaged, instep, you start to feel at household Differences from one culture to another create alienation. This leads to a great deal of emotional distress such as depression, anxiety and helplessness. However, there are various solutions to deal with these symptoms.

Differences from one culture to another create alienation. This leads to a great deal of emotional distress such as depression, anxiety and helplessness. However, there are various solutions to deal with these symptoms.

REFERENCES:

- ms/c/culture-shock.asp#:~:text=of%20Culture%20Shock%3Ehrenworture%20shock%20is%20 typically%20 divided%20 into%20 fourEhrenworture%20shock%20 is%20 typically%20 divided%20 into%20 four%20 Ostages%3A%20the%20honeymoon,homesickness%2C%20adjustment %2C %20and%20acceptance.
4. [https://www.grin.com/document/108360#:~:text=Ehrenw%C3%B6rtliche %20Erkl%C3%A4rung-,,Abstract,through%20during%20an%20international%20 encounter.](https://www.grin.com/document/108360#:~:text=Ehrenw%C3%B6rtliche%20Erkl%C3%A4rung-,,Abstract,through%20during%20an%20international%20 encounter.)